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PRESS AND INJECTION HYBRID MOLDING OF GF/PP HAT-SHAPED MEMBER AND EVALUATION OF ITS BENDING PROPERTY

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INTRODUCTION

GFRTTP : Glass Fiber Reinforced Thermoplastics

- Affordable cost compared to CFRTP (Carbon Fiber Reinforced Thermoplastics)

Press and injection hybrid molding

- Press molding: Outer shell laminate
 - Continuous fiber reinforced laminate
- Injection molding: Rib structure
 - Short or long fiber reinforced thermoplastics

MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Material

- GF/PP laminate (TEPEX, Bond Laminates, $V_f = 47\%$, Thickness = 1.5 mm, 2.0mm)
- PP pellet (MA3, Japan Polypropylene Co. Ltd)
- GF/PP pellet (HG30U, Japan Polypropylene Co. Ltd)

Molding conditions

Finite element analysis

- Solid Mechanics (Structural Mechanics Module) of COMSOL Multiphysics®

Three-point bending test

- Displacement speed:
 5.3×10^{-5} m/s

	Injection material	Injection volume [cm ³]	Cost [US\$]
T0-PP	PP	192	0.32
T1.5-PP		135	12
T2.0-PP		117	2.1
T0-GF/PP	GF/PP	192	0.80
T1.5-GF/PP		135	12
T2.0-GF/PP		117	22

RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

1. Hybrid molded structures using thicker continuous glass fiber reinforced laminate showed higher specific stiffness and the bending stiffness is successfully predicted by the finite analysis.
2. Although the difference in the material cost between T1.5-PP and T1.5-GF/PP and between T2.0-PP and T2.0-GF/PP is only 2 % and 5 %, respectively, the specific stiffness value was 14 % and 24 % higher for molded products using the GF/PP resin for injection material.